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Methodology Proposal for Evaluation of Vigor in Soybean Seeds by Respiratory Activity

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Abstract

The respiratory activity is one of the first biological manifestations of vigor loss in seeds. Detecting loss of seed vigor can help to monitor and control seed production by the seed industry. This research aimed to develop and validate a novel method using carbon dioxide concentration to evaluate vigor of Glycine max [(L.) Merrill] seeds. The proposed method measures CO₂ released by seeds with infrared through a carrier and exhaustion system in a closed system. Samples of 25 seeds of six seed lots of cultivar CD 2737 RR were incubated at temperatures of 15, 25 and 40 °C. The CO₂ released after 1, 3, 6, 9, 12 and 24 h of seed incubation was quantified as well as the percentage of normal seedlings emerged in the field. We calculated the simple correlation coefficients between the two tests. We evaluated the precision and accuracy of the proposed method using 15 seed lots. For the evaluation of the respiratory activity in G. max seeds, we recommend a sample of 25 seeds, incubated at 15 °C for a minimum of 9 h. The method allows to classify seed lots with different levels of vigor and predict the establishment of seedlings in the field. The tested method is appropriated for measuring CO₂ as it externalizes precision between successive measurements and agrees with a reference method.

Keywords: Carbon dioxide; Glycine max [(L.) Merrill], infrared spectroscopy, physiological potential of seeds, validation method

INTRODUCTION

Vigor tests are one of the tools used by the seed industry, aiming to eliminate seed lots with low quality. Germination test, despite being used to assess seed quality does not evaluate possible physiological, biochemical, physical and ontogenetic manifestations associated with decay, limiting the success prognosis in establishing seeds in the field when environmental conditions deviate from the most appropriate (Dode et al., 2013).

In aged seeds, there is an increase in total peroxide accumulation and in the malondialdehyde content, and a decrease in the activity of antioxidant enzymes such as peroxidase, catalase, ascorbate peroxidase, glutathione reductase and superoxide dismutase that operate in the ascorbate-glutathione cycle (Goel et al., 2003). The decrease in the content and activity of those enzymes reduces respiratory capacity because mitochondria are the main site of synthesis and removal of reactive forms of oxygen (ROS), thus highlighting the tolerance of seeds to oxidative stress (Bewley et al., 2013; Xin et al., 2014). Therefore, seed respiration has been used as an index of seed vigor and has good correlation with the development in the field (Patanè et al., 2006).

The ROS accumulation limits protein import capacity by mitochondria to support ontogenetic processes such as the morphology of the mitochondrial crests (Law et al., 2014), the stability of cell membranes (Weitbrecht et al., 2011), and the energy requirement is now directed to the production of remover systems in seeds of lower physiological potential (Patanè & Avola, 2013). As the temperature has a direct effect on the accumulation of ROS (Xin et al., 2014), its handling enables to detect differences in respiratory activity with greater sensitivity.

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The respiratory activity can be measured by oxygen uptake through calorimetry and carbon dioxide (CO₂) content released by the respiratory process via titration, blooming and gas chromatography (Edelstein et al., 2001; Buckley & Huang, 2011; Dode et al., 2013). However, those tests demand time and skilled labor, and have high operating costs, limiting its diffusion in seed testing. Additionally, the results are divergent with respect to the association of vigor with the concentration of carbon dioxide released. Carbon dioxide can also be measured by means of infrared spectroscopy (Vermeulen et al., 2013; Patanè & Avola, 2013; Dantas et al., 2015). This technology makes it possible to analyze non-destructive samples and repeated measurements of a single seed or even a seed sample, whether in dry state or with ongoing germination in a short time. However, there is little information about its use in the evaluation of seed vigor.

The proposed method is based on the detection of CO₂ content by infrared through a drag system and exhaustion of the gas released by the seed maintained in a closed system up to the detection chamber of the gas meter. The gas meter chamber remains with constant flow and CO₂ concentration, serving as a baseline, as gas chromatography. When content dragging occurs, it is possible to detect and build a peak similar to a chromatogram, whose area is its content, thus being comparable.

The hypothesis tested was if adverse temperatures allow separating *G. max* seeds with similar germination in vigor levels through CO₂ concentration and if the developed method is precise and accurate enough to be adopted in laboratory routines. Therefore, this research aimed to develop and validate a novel system using carbon dioxide concentration to evaluate vigor of *Glicine max* [(L.) Merrill] seeds.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Seed Sample

We used six lots of *G. max* from cultivar CD 2737 RR supplied by Central Cooperative of Agricultural Research (Cooperativa Central de Pesquisa Agrícola) - COODETEC. Seeds were held on screens of 6.0 and 6.5 mm with a moisture content of $9.4 \pm 0.3\%$ and 153.4 ± 19.7 g for the average weight of one thousand seeds. Seeds were untreated with pesticides. During the experiment, seeds were placed in kraft paper bags and stored in a dry chamber adjusted to 20 ± 2 °C, with relative humidity of $40 \pm 3\%$.

Seed germination test was conducted with four replications of 100 seeds in germitest paper, moistened with a deionized water volume of 2.5 times the mass of the germitest paper. We used paper rolls in a seed germinator (Mangelsdorf) at 25.0 ± 2.0 °C with a photoperiod of 12 h. Results were expressed as percentage of normal seedlings obtained on the eighth day after sowing, as recommended by the Rules for Seed Analysis (Brasil, 2009).

Vigor was evaluated by the accelerated aging, tetrazolium, and the electrical conductivity tests.

The accelerated aging test was conducted, as recommended by AOSA (2002). Four replicates of 42 g of seeds from each lot were spread evenly over a plastic screen fixed in a plastic gerbox containing 40 mL of water. The boxes with seeds were closed and maintained at 41 °C for 72 h. Later, the germination test was carried out as described above.

For the evaluation of vigor by the tetrazolium test, four replications of 50 seeds were soaked in germination paper, moistened with water equivalent to 2.5 times its mass for 24 h at room temperature. Then, the seeds were accommodated in a 50 mL plastic cup and added to a solution of 2, 3, 5-triphenyl tetrazolium chloride at 0.075% and kept in a chamber type BOD at 40 °C for 3 h, then washed in running water and analyzed individually (França Neto et al., 1998).

The electrical conductivity test was, according to AOSA (2002), using four replications of 50 seeds, packaged in containers with 75 mL of deionized water at 25 °C for 24 h.

At the same time, field emergency test was conducted using four blocks of 100 seeds sown in November 2013, in furrows of 5.0 m long x 3.0 cm deep, spaced 30 cm without irrigation. The percentage of normal seedlings emerged was computed on the fifteenth day after sowing (Nakagawa, 1994).

Quantification of CO₂ was performed by evaluating the CO₂ content released during respiration, with the aid of a gas exchange meter IRGA (LI-COR 6400 XT). Coupled to the equipment, a system of injection and

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airflow, free of CO₂, was mounted with an air compressor with an airflow adjusted to 140 mL·min⁻¹, which injects air into a 50 mL flask filled with soda-lime and properly sealed with rubber septum for injection. Connecting the system formed by the compressor, container with soda lime, and sample bottle, plastic hoses with 3.0 mm diameter and 15 cm length were used, and in the extremities, disposable hypodermic needles (1.6 mm x 40 mm) were coupled. The apparatus was combined with a plastic hose segment with the same characteristics described above, with one end fixed in the IRGA gas chamber and the other introduced into the sample bottle. Thus, at the reading, two needles were introduced into the sample bottle, and then the airflow system was connected simultaneously with the equipment.

In the preparation of the sample, four replicates 25 seeds were used, accommodated in 50 mL glass containers, then added deionized water, with volume to achieve humidity of 20% (m/m) according to Equation 1, then closed with rubber septa for injection and properly sealed. Afterward, the containers were incubated in BOD chambers at temperatures of 15, 25 and 40 °C. In the end, the degree of humidity reached by the mass increment was quantified.

$$WV(g) = \left[\left(SW - \frac{SW - (SW \cdot SM / 100)}{1 - (0.01 \cdot MCA)} \right) \right] \quad (1)$$

Where: SW - Weight Sample (g); SM seed moisture content (%); MCA - moisture content to be achieved (%); WV – water volume.

Readings of CO₂ concentration were performed at 1, 3, 6, 9, 12, and 24 h incubation. To obtain the value of each repetition, the equipment was programmed to log the CO₂ concentration every 0.5 s until the complete exhaustion of the contents. The gas analyzer chamber was kept with a constant concentration of 380 μmol·CO₂ at a flow rate of 500 μmol·s⁻¹. With the values for each repetition, the gas peaks were adjusted to a log-normal distribution and the peak area was obtained, according to Equation 2 (Felinger, 1998) and the results expressed in mmol of CO₂ per gram of seeds.

$$f(t) = \frac{A}{x} \text{ EXP} \left[-0.5 \left(\frac{\ln(t-t_0)}{\sigma} \right)^2 \right] \quad (2)$$

Where: A = peak area (μmol·CO₂);

In the evaluation of the physiological quality, the experiment followed a completely randomized design. Field emergence followed a randomized block design. We used t test to compare the percentage of normal seedlings obtained in the germination test with the percentage at the end of the accelerated aging test. Additionally, the Tocher optimization method was applied, using the mean Euclidean distance as a measure of dissimilarity between the results of vigor tests.

We analyzed CO₂ concentration with a randomized block in a factorial design (6 x 6) composed of six seed lots, six incubation periods. The incubation temperature factor was analyzed separately. The data were checked for normality of distribution by the Shapiro-Wilk test, and for the homogeneity of variance by Bartlett test. Later, the data were subjected to analysis of variance. When statistically significant differences have detected the mean among lots were grouped by the Scott-Knott test at 5% probability of error. For the time period effect we used regression analysis.

Subsequently, we calculated the simple correlation coefficients between CO₂ concentration with field emergence at 5% error probability by the t test.

Validation of the method of carbon dioxide concentration

We applied parameters of validation of precision and accuracy proposed by ISO 5725-2 (ISO, 1994). For that purpose, we used fifteen lots of *G. max* from cultivar CD 2737 RR supplied by the Central Cooperative of Agricultural Research - COODETEC from 2013 held in 6.0 sieve with the moisture of 7.8 ± 0.8 %.

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The CO₂ concentration was obtained in 20 replicates of 25 seeds each that were accommodated in 50 mL glass container with deionized water sufficient to achieve humidity of 20%, according to Equation 1. The flasks were then closed with a rubber septum for injection and properly sealed. The containers were incubated in BOD chambers at 15 °C for 12 h. The expression of results was similar to that described in determination of CO₂ concentration item.

We submitted the results to Grubbs test at 95% probability of error for detection of outliers.

The precision analysis occurred by the repeatability analysis by comparing the critical limit of repeatability (LCR) with the total amplitude (\hat{A}) and by the analysis of variance. For that purpose, we read 10 samples from the same seed lot on two different days. We compared the days of analysis per seed lot with an analysis of variance at 5% error probability.

The accuracy analysis occurred by comparing methods, using the gas chromatography results as a reference. We calculated the relative standard deviation and the simple correlation coefficient between the results obtained by infrared method and by gas chromatography (reference). Additionally, the t test at 5% probability of error was applied to compare the methods.

For quantification of CO₂ concentration by gas chromatography, 2 mL samples were extracted from three replicates per seed lot with the aid of a gastight® syringe (LT 2.5 mL and KF PT 5 needle - Hamilton) and injected into a gas chromatograph (Finnigan 9001®) equipped with a methanator, flame ionization detector and capillary column Rt- QPLOT® (30 m/0.53 mm Restek). The temperatures of the oven, the detector, the methanator, and the injector were at 60, 250, 350 and 90 °C respectively. The flow of N₂, H₂, and air were 25, 20 and 175 mL·min⁻¹ respectively with constant pressure of the carrier gas (N₂) at 15 psi. The quantification of the CO₂ concentration was made by comparing the chromatographic peak areas of the samples and the standard, and the results were expressed in mmol CO₂ g⁻¹.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Determination of the carbon dioxide concentration

Evaluation of seed physiological quality showed no differences (p>0.05) in the percentage of normal seedlings from germination test (Table 1). The average percentage of normal seedlings was 78%, which is above the minimum percentage of germination (75%) recommended by the Normative Instruction 45/2013 of the Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Food Supply which deals with the establishment of standards of identity and quality for production and marketing of *G. max* seeds in Brazil (Brasil, 2013).

Table 1: Percentage of normal seedlings in the germination test (NS), accelerated aging test (AA), vigor by the tetrazolium test (TZv), electrical conductivity test (EC) and field emergence (FE) of six lots of *G. max* seeds cv. CD 2737 RR.

Lot	NS	AA	TZv	EC	FE
	----- % -----			μS·cm·g ⁻¹	---- % ----
1	81 a*	64 a**	61 b	165.49 a	61 b
2	82 a	56 a**	61 b	170.91 a	57 b
3	80 a	61 a**	62 b	160.21 a	64 b
4	75 a	60 a**	64 b	156.78 a	63 b
5	78 a	66 a**	70 a	149.58 b	68 a
6	75 a	76 a	70 a	138.56 b	70 a
CV (%)	8.6	11.0	2.9	5.6	7.2

*Means followed by the same letter in the column do not differ statistically from each other at the level of 5% probability of error by Scott-Knott test. **Significant at 5% probability of error by the t test.

There were no differences (p>0.05) among the seed lots to the percentage of normal seedlings obtained from the accelerated aging test (Table 1). However, comparing the results of the germination test with the

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accelerated aging, for each seed lot it is observed that only lot 6 did not show ($p > 0.05$) in the loss of initial feasibility, indicating higher tolerance to adverse conditions of artificial aging. The reduction rates in viability ranged from 5 to 32% for lots 6 and 2, respectively after artificial aging. It is noteworthy that the seed lots had similar moisture content at the end of the accelerated aging test ($26.7 \pm 0.4\%$).

In the evaluation of seed vigor by the tetrazolium and electrical conductivity tests, it was possible to segregate lots 5 and 6, which had the highest percentage of seeds with no visual damage and less leakage of electrolytes across cell membranes (Table 1).

Based on the results of vigor tests, it was possible to group the six lots in two quality groups, indicating that lots 5 and 6 are those with higher physiological quality. This behavior was extended to the evaluation of performance in the field, evidenced by the higher percentage of normal seedlings emerged (Table 1). It is also noteworthy that the contribution of the variables to the composition of the groups was 17.6, 32.3 and 50.1% for the results of vigor by the accelerated aging test, vigor by the tetrazolium test and the electrical conductivity test, respectively.

There was an increase in the release of CO_2 due to the incubation temperature (40°C), which resulted in an increase in the CO_2 release about 2.8 and 1.6 times higher compared to samples incubated at 15°C and 25°C (Fig. 1).

The CO_2 concentration as a function of the incubation period was adjusted to a sigmoidal model of three parameters for the different temperatures (Fig.1). Seeds incubated at 15°C yielded the point of maximum inflection of the curve with 13.1 h. This period of time indicates that from this moment on, the increase in CO_2 concentration is minimum, and stability begins, culminating in the baseline which was estimated at 57 h. On the other hand, recognition of the maximum inflection point allows determining the maximum time required for the test to be interrupted because there is no significant accumulation of CO_2 .

Fig. 1. The concentration of CO_2 released from *G. max* seeds cv. CD 2737 RR in function of the incubation temperature and the incubation time period.

In seeds incubated at 25°C , the point of maximum inflection of the curve was achieved with 15.5 h and baseline with 75.2 h. For seeds incubated at 40°C (Fig. 1), the point of maximum inflection of the curve was achieved with 11.7 h and baseline with 52.1 h.

In monocot seeds, the oxygen requirement is lower to promote germination compared to dicots, but in oilseeds such as soybeans, the lower oxygen pressure results in loss of decarboxylative potential (Rosental et

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al., 2014). Therefore, the evaluation of soybean seeds at 40 °C can limit the actual detection of respiratory activity.

Dry seeds lack an organized system of membranes, and as the hydration advances, recovery of mitochondrial structure occurs, which become more efficient in decarboxylation and oxidative phosphorylation (Law et al., 2014). Maintenance of seed vigor can be directly associated with: 1. hydration time required for mitochondria to become more efficient, and 2. showing a better-organized membrane system, 3. stable rates of O₂ absorption and CO₂ release (Bewley et al. 2013), indicated by the maximum inflection point as shown in Fig. 1.

The sensitivity for detecting significant differences among different seed lots incubated at 15 °C was directly proportional to the incubation time. As for samples, three groups are formed from the 12 h of incubation (Table 2).

Table 2: Concentration of CO₂ released from *G. max* cv. CD 2737 RR seeds as a function of the temperature, lot and incubation time, and its correlation (r) with the percentage of the emergence of seedlings in the field.

Temperature (°C)	Lots	Incubation period (h)					
		1	3	6	9	12	24
		----- mmol·g ⁻¹ -----					
15	1	0.13a	1.11a	2.74a	3.70a	4.42a	5.88a
	2	0.14a	1.10a	2.67a	3.60a	4.27a	5.52a
	3	0.20a	1.17a	2.68a	3.46a	4.18a	5.44a
	4	0.18a	1.11a	2.70a	3.06b	3.93b	5.16b
	5	0.14a	1.11a	2.59a	2.94b	3.54c	4.85c
	6	0.18a	0.98a	2.51a	2.80b	3.56c	4.82c
CV (%)		6.6					
r		-0.45	-0.46	-0.79	-0.85**	-0.86**	-0.87**
25	1	0.29a	2.72a	4.49a	5.42a	6.43a	9.49a
	2	0.28a	2.78a	4.43a	5.60a	6.06a	9.04a
	3	0.27a	2.86a	4.43a	5.24a	6.49a	9.40a
	4	0.26a	2.82a	4.41a	5.37a	6.19a	8.72b
	5	0.23a	2.70a	4.33a	5.00a	5.99a	8.64b
	6	0.23a	2.79a	4.32a	4.90a	5.80a	8.36b
CV (%)		9.0					
r		0.04	-0.06	-0.79	-0.98**	-0.45	-0.63
40	1	0.29a	2.72a	4.49a	5.42a	6.43a	9.49a
	2	0.28a	2.78a	4.43a	5.60a	6.06a	9.04a
	3	0.27a	2.86a	4.43a	5.24a	6.49a	9.40a
	4	0.26a	2.82a	4.41a	5.37a	6.19a	8.72a
	5	0.23a	2.70a	4.33a	5.00b	5.99b	8.64b
	6	0.23a	2.79a	4.32a	4.90b	5.80b	8.36b
CV (%)		8.3					
r		-0.04	-0.46	-0.78	-0.84**	-0.89**	-0.93**

Means followed by the same letter in the column do not differ statistically from each other at the level of 5% probability of error by Scott-Knott test. ** Significant at 5% probability of error by the t test.

It is known that the statistical differences occur because of the lower dispersion of data around the mean, then the seed lots incubated at 15 °C results in an increased accuracy and lower standard deviation and consequently, the variance, favoring the power of analysis and consistency of results.

Additionally, differences in moisture content may enhance or minimize respiratory activity because they favor the increase of the number of active mitochondria and, consequently, influence the results, as occurs in electrical conductivity and accelerated aging tests. In this research, from 3 h of incubation at 15 °C, there was no progress in water absorption, whose moisture content was maintained at 21.2 ± 0.5%, with little variation due to the period of time. In the first hour of incubation, the moisture content remained at 18.8%, respectively.

The incubation at 25 °C did not allow to classify any seed lots for up to 12 h. After 24 h of incubation, differences were detected and the formation of a group composed of seed lots 4, 5, and 6 with the lowest CO₂ concentration.

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The temperature of 25 °C, considered optimal for seed germination, may have hindered the separation of seed lots because the ability of a seed to germinate under a wide temperature limit is a manifestation of its vigor. Therefore, seeds that can tolerate higher thermal variation are the most vigorous and subject to segregation by respiratory activity.

For seeds incubated at 40 °C it was possible to group seed lots 5 and 6, being more evident after 9 h of incubation, whose groups resemble the effect seen in other vigor tests (Table 1). The differences were achieved in the period estimated by the maximum inflection of the adjusted equation. The shorter time required for evaluation at this temperature (11.7 h) compared to that observed with incubation at 15 °C (13.1 h) resulted from the fact that the target moisture content (20%) was reached after 1 hour of incubation, with moisture content remained at $20.7 \pm 0.5\%$, whereas for that temperature it was possible after 3 h of incubation.

Soaking marks the resumption of metabolic activity in dry seeds. The metabolic function quickly recovered in the first hours of hydration is linked to the generation of the redox state (Rosental et al., 2014) and the time required for the seeds to express their potential is variable depending on the genotype and the water potential, since the capacity and the water absorption speed can vary significantly in soybean seed varieties (Costa et al., 2002) and, consequently, in respiration rates.

The analysis of the simple correlation between the values obtained from the CO₂ concentration and percentage of normal seedlings from field test revealed no correlation ($p > 0.05$) between the quantified before 9 h of incubation (Table 2). After 9 h of incubation, seeds samples at temperatures of 15 °C or 40 °C showed significant negative correlation between quantified CO₂ and the percentage of seedlings emerged in the field test, indicating that seeds that release less CO₂ per mass unit are the ones with better performance in the field. The correlation coefficients were on average -0.86 and -0.89 respectively, expressing a correlation considered very high between the parameters (Davis, 1971).

The complete failure of seed germination is the result of deterioration. However, before that state is reached, seeds lose vigor at different rates. Structural changes in biological membranes caused by lipid peroxidation influence viscosity, permeability and cell functions of mitochondria (Weitbrecht et al., 2011). Therefore, the transition from dry to the fluid state of the cell membranes favors rapid diffusion and capillary action of water in aged seeds. On the other hand, advances in faster absorption of water cause the mitochondria, present in dry seeds, to resume their metabolic activity more quickly, resulting in the release of CO₂ in soybean seeds.

The high correlation coefficients between CO₂ concentration and percentage of seedling emergence in the field suggest that the methodology was reliable to predict the establishment of seedlings in the field when kept in conditions of low and high temperature of incubation. However, low temperatures provided the greatest separation of seed lots, resulting in greater sensitivity in the detection of differences in physiological potential of *G. max* seeds, undetected by viability and vigor tests. Therefore, low temperature (15 °C) showed ability to classify seed lots according to their performance potential.

Validation of Analytical Method

The Grubbs test detected the presence of outliers in seed lots 1 and 3 (Fig. 2a), which were removed from other analyses. These outliers are linked to the moisture level reached at the end of the incubation period, which had humidity of 25.3 and 22.1% respectively. The others remained with humidity adjusted to $20.3 \pm 1.2\%$.

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Figure 2. (a) Extreme value test (Grubbs Test) applied to the results of CO₂ concentration in fifteen lots of *G. max* seeds CD 2737 RR. (b) Precision analysis by comparing the critical limit of repeatability (LRC) with the total amplitude (\hat{A}).

The evaluation of precision by comparing the critical limit of repeatability (LRC) indicated for the 15 lots tested an acceptable repeatability because the individual overall amplitude remained below the critical limit (Fig. 2b). These results show the degree of agreement between the results of successive measurements of the same variable (represented by seed lots) made under the same predetermined measurement conditions.

The result of the analysis on separate days (Table 3) indicated significant differences for seed lots 13 and 14. Respiration is an ongoing and increasing process as a function of time of soaking and the availability of water to the seeds (BEWLEY et al., 2013); thus, small delays in reading and addition of the water volume above or below the desired level can result in variations of the quantified content and contribute to the onset of the differences detected in the respective lots.

Table 3: Evaluation of repeatability by comparing the days of analysis by lots of *G. max* seeds CD 2737 RR.

Lots	First day (n=10)	Second day (n=10)	ANOVA		
			Q _{Mdia}	F _{calc}	P _{value}
	----- mmol·g ⁻¹ -----				
1	6.24 ± 0.36	6.43 ± 0.78	0.1850	0.5000	0.489
2	5.81 ± 0.53	6.11 ± 0.67	0.4560	1.1880	0.290
3	5.56 ± 0.54	5.35 ± 0.41	0.2110	0.9280	0.348
4	5.22 ± 0.38	5.46 ± 0.35	0.2780	2.0670	0.168
5	5.18 ± 0.72	5.21 ± 0.50	0.0052	0.0134	0.909
6	5.16 ± 0.40	5.24 ± 0.44	0.0353	0.2030	0.658
7	3.72 ± 0.61	3.43 ± 0.61	0.3990	1.2390	0.280
8	3.39 ± 0.49	3.39 ± 0.45	0.0242	0.1340	0.719
9	3.54 ± 0.37	3.64 ± 0.38	0.0497	0.3500	0.561
10	3.33 ± 0.53	3.17 ± 0.32	0.1450	0.7700	0.392
11	2.85 ± 0.27	3.03 ± 0.35	0.1600	1.2260	0.283
12	2.91 ± 0.23	3.02 ± 0.29	0.0603	0.9010	0.355
13	2.93 ± 0.21	3.26 ± 0.23	0.5360	5.8630	0.026
14	2.69 ± 0.18	2.95 ± 0.20	0.3670	8.9760	0.008
15	3.33 ± 0.30	3.35 ± 0.38	0.2040	0.8970	0.355

Where: Q_{Mday} = mean square for the purpose of the working day; T_{calc} = calculated value of F test; p = probability of significance.

Accuracy analysis showed agreement between the results from the infrared with the gas chromatography (reference method) as no differences were detected (p >0.05) by the t test (Table 4). Furthermore, the relative standard deviation was less than 9% among seed lots, inherent to the mass method, since deterioration is a single physiological process and a high coefficient of correlation between the methods (R = 0,97).

Table 4: Analysis of accuracy between the average CO₂ concentration by the reference method with the method proposed by the relative standard deviation (RSD), by the t test and the simple correlation (R) in 15 lots of *G. max* CD 2737 RR.

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Lot	Reference method (n=3)	Proposed method (n=20)	RSD	P _t test
	----- mmol·g ⁻¹ -----		--- % ---	
1	6.57 ± 0.28	6.33 ± 0.60	3.6	0.20
2	6.46 ± 0.33	5.97 ± 0.62	7.6	0.19
3	5.79 ± 0.43	5.45 ± 0.48	5.8	0.10
4	5.66 ± 0.38	5.34 ± 0.76	5.6	0.66
5	4.93 ± 0.26	5.20 ± 0.60	5.3	0.24
6	5.14 ± 0.48	5.19 ± 0.41	1.2	0.46
7	3.81 ± 0.19	3.58 ± 0.57	6.2	0.19
8	3.66 ± 0.11	3.35 ± 0.41	8.5	0.11
9	3.54 ± 0.44	3.59 ± 0.37	1.4	0.15
10	3.44 ± 0.07	3.25 ± 0.43	5.3	0.48
11	2.89 ± 0.24	2.94 ± 0.36	1.7	0.22
12	2.95 ± 0.13	2.96 ± 0.26	0.8	0.88
13	3.01 ± 0.02	3.10 ± 0.34	2.9	0.66
14	2.97 ± 0.17	2.82 ± 0.24	0.7	0.10
15	3.66 ± 0.22	3.34 ± 0.28	8.6	0.09
R	0.97 p < 0.0001			

Where: p_t test and p = probability of significance by two-tailed t test.

CONCLUSIONS

For the evaluation of the respiratory activity in *G. max* seeds by CO₂ concentration, it is recommended a sample of 25 seeds, incubated at 15 °C for a minimum of 9 h, which allows classifying seed lots with different levels of vigor and predict the establishment of seedlings in the field.

Based on the intra-laboratory validation, this protocol is suitable for the measurement of CO₂ in seeds, because it shows precision between successive measurements and correlation to the reference method.

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